

Rescuing Lost Souls at Sea: Marconi's Pivotal Role in the Birth of Public Protection and Disaster Relief

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Abstract—The need for a specific regulation concerning the transmission and reception of distress signals was an entirely new topic that was developed after the invention of the radio. Before the first years of the XX century, the international regulation did not address it. It was with the deployment of radio equipment at sea that the opportunity was perceived.

In this contribution we show the outcomes of our studies about the development of this completely new approach to the safety of the vessels. We specifically analyze the documents that relate the activity of Guglielmo Marconi in this field. We are interested in providing evidence that at the beginning of that Century, the Italian entrepreneur had understood that radio communication provided a wider range of opportunities than ground telegraphy. Moreover, we wish to point out what are the areas of study that should be explored in the future to clarify whether Marconi was a pioneer in this field too, or whether the disaster recovery and safety at sea was broadly perceived as an opportunity of human advance.

Keywords— *Public Protection and Disaster Relief, PPDR, Convention radiotélégraphique internationale, Convention télégraphique internationale, Radiocommunications, Maritime Distress*

I. INTRODUCTION

At the turn of the XIX Century, telegraphy and telephony were well established technologies. Their development was perceived to improve the quality of life and the welfare of the nations. Additionally, their effectiveness was so internationally recognized to overcome the nationalisms in view of a progressive world.

It is therefore surprising that Public Protection was not among the themes that were standardized by the international agreements. Reading the Saint Peterborough Convention, no mention can be found concerning the need of establishing any specific signaling, nor of specifically dealing with communications that bring information of risk, danger, incident, or disaster. Both encrypted and high priority forms of communication were devised, but the power of communications to deliver relief in case of a disaster was completely held silent. We did not carry a specific study on the development of such forms of communications using either telegraphy, or telephony: this study has been promoted in the evidence that a sharp change in the way the communication was intended happened at the Berlin Convention on Radio Telegraphy in 1903.

In the preliminary acts of that convention, we can discover the question whether a specific approach had to be devised in case of the need of communicating a distress situation. This approach led to a completely novel protocol to be established in such cases.

It can be assumed that this protocol was the natural consequence of the evolution of the telegraphic protocols, and, as such, the final acts of the Berlin Convention of 1903 were the natural consequence of a new opportunity that was not achievable before that date.

In the authors' view, the introduction of the new protocol is the result of a shift in understanding the meaning of the communication. The international delegates made two evolutionary passages for telecommunications. The first was recognizing the new opportunity brought by radio innovation in the field. The second was that the Public Protection communication was a completely autonomous communication service.

Presently we read these two passages as one, and the evidence is in the acts and the final resolution of the Berlin preparatory Conference.

Therefore, we collect multiple international sources and bring their evidence together trying to highlight that what appears as just an opportunistic regulation, rather was the outcome of a complex intuition. This intuition is composed of the novelty of a communication means and of the understanding of a specific coding requirement for the effective transmission reception of a distress signal.

Ultimately, we try to provide the elements that may guide the academia to focus on the personality of Guglielmo Marconi as the first person that had this intuition.

In the following we propose the evidence that we have collected about the complex nature of evolution that arose at the 1903 Berlin Conference. Then, we will propose some new studies to be undertaken in order to establish the reference context

where the PPDR moved its first steps. Then we will collect some general conclusion about the importance of this new study and the significance it has in the present and future of communications.

II. THE EVIDENCES

The “Conférence Radiotélégraphique Internationale de Berlin” (1906) introduced the concept of distress relief by means of radiocommunications.

Article 9. of the 1906 “Convention” states: «Les stations radiotélégraphiques sont obligées d'accepter par priorité absolue les appels de détresse provenant des navires, de répondre de même à ces appels et d'y donner la suite qu'ils comportent.»

The 1906 “Convention” applies a large number of articles of the “Convention Télégraphique Internationale de Saint-Petersbourg” (1875): in view of the different nature of the operations involved in the transmission and the reception of radio signals, the annexed Regulation are specifically adopted. These Regulations recognized the Morse signal of transmission and introduced the “... — — — ...” (SOS) distress sequence to extend the range of possible messages to the ones required to identify the situation of a vessel in distress. It is not of secondary importance that the Regulations apply to the radiotelegraphy and that only vessels could issue the distress signals.

This complex set of rules has been popularly simplified attaching a meaning to the distress signal. Here we need to stress that attached meaning has reduced the significance of the distress signal to a sequence of letters. Reading the 1906 “Convention” it is clear that Article XV of the Regulations stress on the importance that a new class of messages is established “and” a new procedure put in existence. We note that these two rules bring emergency telecommunications to life.

Carrying with itself such a profound outcome, it is relevant to understand whether this new class was precognised and intended or rather the new class was the unavoidable aftermath of a generally well understood new opportunity arisen from the development of the radio communications. In other words, whether we can recognize a deep understanding of the meaning of what we commonly describe today as mobile communications or whether it was the acknowledgment of a technical opportunity.

In the following of this Section, we will move backward in time to support the first view, and to some extent to pose the basis to recognize to Guglielmo Marconi the sparkling idea of a radio also thought to support Public Protection and Disaster Relief.

This backward trip, commences in 1905, and it is documented in the “Journal Télégraphique” of the “Bureau International des Administration Télégraphique”, which corresponds to the present “ITU News Magazine”. In the September issue the review published in the “Publications Officielles” the “Instructions du Reichspostamt de l'Empire d'Allemagne à l'usage de la radiotélégraphie pour la correspondance privée”. This national Regulations made reference to the already mentioned Saint-Petersbourg Convention, as modified by the 1903 London Convention, in the path of the analogy between the telegraphy and the radio-telegraphy. This analogy is reprised also with respect to the already established German regulations about telegraphy. A couple of new signals are added to the method of transmission. the first is the “Détresse” signal and the second is the “Quête” signal, respectively “... — — — ...” (SOS) and “... — — — ...” (SOE) These signals could only be transmitted by vessels in distress. This regulation anticipated the outcomes of the following year Conference in Berlin, imposing the priority in the order of transmission and relaying of these kind of signals.

What is established here is the special nature of the distress signal. Clearly, the lack of any specific mentions among the pages of the monthly international review about this special arrangement, it is not the evidence of an established course of action in the field of disaster recovery. Nevertheless any presence would have undoubtedly clarified that the principles of DR were born with these Regulations. As a consequence, the search for a paternity of the idea of radio signal for distress and the novel opportunity for radio telegraphy (and telegraphy in general) to provide DR is displaced backwards in time.

Although the narrative of the conference is based on the willingness of the Emperor of Germany to repair a diplomatic accident caused by the failure in the reception of a formal message, the participants to the event - with the important exception of Italy, and, to a smaller degree, of Great Britain - appeared unprepared for the revolutionary contributions that radio was ready to offer. We support the idea that the premises for the preliminary radio conference were based on a miscomprehension of the potential of radio.

Mitglieder der internationalen Konferenz für drahtlose Telegraphie - 1903.

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We find ourselves reading a very preliminary draft of a properly effective radio regulations.

The working documents circulated at the beginning of the Conference posed the question that we have seen fully developed in the Regulations of the 1906 Conference.

We can read: “Faut-il créer des prérogatives en faveur des navires en détresse?”. How these prerogatives could become effective is unknown.

Similarly, it is interesting the question posed with respect to military stations: “Toutefois ne conviendrait-il pas de leur imposer le devoir de prêter, autant que possible, assistance aux navires en danger?” The evidence is that the intervention is expected regardless of the nationality of the vessel in distress. Soon, this requirement was dropped, and it was equally discussed, but dismissed in the 1906 Conference. Therefore, we are led to think that the Conference had not reached the understanding of the true extent of the radio revolution, and it was unable to develop it. The Acts of the Conference can not help us in perceiving the actual motivation that drove the call for an international meeting. The perceived sense that comes out from the verbal process is that of a willingness to balance the technological progress among the participants: this process is strongly fought against by Italy, in a less strenuous fashion by the United Kingdom.

We come to this feeling reading the intervention of the UK delegate, Mr. Lamb, whose nation is specifically interested in guaranteeing the commercial exploitability of the radio invention. On the contrary, the verbal process contains a complex intervention of Mr. Bonomo of the Italian delegation, presented in the form of a letter sent to the Conference President and then read during the seats.

The “Capitano di Corvetta” Quintino Bonomo del Casale is the author of the diary that collects the experiments of the Italian Navy with the Marconi equipment. In his book, Mr. Bonomo presents the test carried at sea and the technical adversities faced during the evaluation process of the Marconi solution. First, he always presented the action he was witnessing as a means to test the quality of a communication instrument. Not a military communication equipment, but an equipment that can be properly configured in order to become a military tool.

We can find traces of this approach especially when the book of Mr. Bonomo deals with questions related to the positioning of the transmitting and receiving equipments. But clear evidence of the general purpose of the experiments and of the expectations of the author can be found in the title and the subtitle of the book (“TELEGRAFIA SENZA FILI - ESPERIENZE ESEGUITE NELL’ALTO TIRRENO DAL 1° SETTEMBRE 1900 AL 18 MAGGIO 1901”), where no mentioning is made to the facts that the tests were carried under the support of the Navy; as well as in the Introduction, where the initial words are “Questo lavoro che . già, sotto altra forma, fu oggetto di una rela-zione al Ministero della marina e che oggi è onorato dell’ospitalità della Rivista Marittima, è dedicato ai miei colleghi della marina”. That is, the work is dedicated to the navy colleagues, not to the military navy colleagues.

Before analyzing the point of interest of the letter, it is worth recalling the content of the preliminary notes with respect to the obligations to be fulfilled by military stations. At the end of the Conference, no obligation was confirmed for the military vessels. The verbal process shows the interest of a convergent regulatory approach between the civil and the military radio communications: the reactions to this approach were then amplified because of the issues concerning the obligations of relaying messages among different radio communications equipments, having different performances. Therefore a question is raised: which nation did introduce the proposal for the obligation of military vessels to give priority to the distress signals? At the authors’ state of knowledge, we do not have an exact response to this question. It is by deductive way that we suggest that the point of safety at sea, regardless of the kind of communications was a point of interest of the Italian and to a lesser extent of the UK delegation (see the words of Mr. Lamb with this respect), both technically and commercially bounded to the figure of Guglielmo Marconi.

We have the content of the letter of Mr. Bonomo to support our intuition. The complex, yet verbal description, was aimed at explaining the entirely new landscape posed to the world of communications by the introduction of radio. In his intervention Mr. Bonomo clearly identifies the problems of: spectrum regulation; interference control; out of band emission. The terms used are rather distant from our contemporary understanding of the matter. His letter shows the gap in understanding existing between, Italy, as a leading country in radio technology and the others. Likewise, the letters shows the perceived sense of necessity for efficiency versus the compelled necessity of taking act.

It comes not as surprise then reading the following statement: “Il y a un cas qui mérite toute notre attention, c’est celui des signaux d’urgence des navires en détresse.

Dans ce cas toutes les stations devraient être obligées de faire leur possible pour les recevoir; et je crois qu’il serait utile de s’accorder dans cette conférence sur la méthode à suivre. Pourtant nous proposons la norme suivante.

Un navire en détresse devrait envoyer à intervalles de quelques minutes le signal SSSDDD. Toutes les stations qui recevraient ce signal devraient suspendre leurs communications et passer toute de suite à la réception; au plus tôt elles se mettraient en communication avec le navire en commençant la transmission par le même signal SSSDDD.”

These are not the words of a “Capitano di Corvetta”; these are the words of the representative of a group that forwards a new understanding in the field of radiocommunications. Here we have the first concrete envisioning of Disaster Relief communications. No doubt the Italian Navy and Mr. Marconi had envisioned the distress signal. No restriction is made on the nature of the receiving station, whether civil or military. The distress signal is a novel branch of global radiocommunications, suggested by the words of the Italian delegate.

Was it a Mr. Bonomo idea: hardly. At least we are not driven to think this way reading his book. The great advantage of radiocommunications in perilous conditions is identified there when heavy fog diminishes the sight, either at day or at night.

III. A GUIDELINE FOR FURTHER STUDIES

We are now at the turning point of the history of DR communications. Here we encounter the figure of Mr. Marconi, and from here we try to understand his vision.

As a principal remark we must read the words of the President of the 1903 Preliminary Conference, when he describes in his opening remarks the duty of the delegates with respect to the theme of the safety of the vessels at sea, as well when he repeatedly suggests the delaying of any decision concerning the distress matters.

A secondary one is related to the intervention of Mr. Bourdignon of the French delegation who poses a question about the expected monetary allowance for the reception of the distress signal that could in principle be requested by the receiving party. This question has really no answer, as the French delegate recognised himself. In fact, we may presently safely conclude, we are not speaking of monetary value, we are speaking of safety of people. These joint arguments allow us to dismiss as nonsensical the hypothesis that the distress signaling introduced or at least fiercely supported by the Italian delegation was meant to attain a gain of the Marconi system.

Because of the premises of the previous Section, and because of these remarks, we decided to devote ourself to the research of elements that could provide evidence for the paternity of the ideas related to Disaster Recovery.

We have a couple of important indirect information about the role of Mr. Marconi in the envisioning of the Distress relief, and this is the reason why we call for a novel guideline to improve our current knowledge of the topic.

The first information is related to The Marconi International Marine Communication Company Limited establishment. The Marine Company was established in April 1900 less than three years after Marconi's first company and this proves that the early development of wireless involved its maritime application well before the great resonance that rescuing people at sea brought. The Berlin Preliminary Conference is three years in the future at this point in time. As it was stated in the prospectus of the company: 'Mr. Marconi's wireless telegraphy will not only add to the safety and security of the vast fleets of passenger and trading vessels navigating all seas; but it may reasonably be anticipated that it will be the means of creating a sea telegraph business which will add considerably to the revenue of the existing Government telegraphs. The directors will endeavour to work hand in hand with all Governments whose interests seem for the most part identical with those of the Company.'

The view expressed by this document put forward the benefit of a more secure navigation with respect to the benefits of the revenue stemming from a radiotelegraphy business. The document is contemporary of the experiments reported by Mr. Bonomo, and all of the military evolution of radio telegraphy is further put in the background, at the least. The other investors of the Company were related to the bank and the insurance sectors: seen at the light of this knowledge, the "safety first" statement appears as it had been written having in mind the reduction of the risk by means of increasing the resistance to threats. Additionally, recalling that the 1903 Berlin Preliminary Conference moved the focal point from the potential benefit arising for a single shipowner by means of the use of the radio telegraphy to a general common advantage, the wording used in the prospectus appears to anticipate this shift in point of view.

The second indirect information is even earlier in time. We owe to Dunlap the report of an interview to Mr. Marconi appeared on McClure's Magazine, in June, 1899. Mr. Marconi is reported saying "a boat in distress would want everyone hear its call." And subsequently: "My system allows messages to be sent from one moving train to another moving train or to a fixed point alongside the tracks; to be sent from one moving vessel to another vessel or to the shore, and from lighthouses or signal stations to vessels in fog or distress.[...] Imagine a lighthouse or danger spot in the sea fitted with a transmitter and parabolic reflector, the impulses in the ether-a series of danger signals. It is evident that any vessel equipped with a receiver could get warning, perhaps by the automatic ringing of a bell before her lookout could see a light or hear a fog-horn."

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